

CNDO/S Study of Fluoromethanes

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The results of CNDO/S with limited configuration interaction calculations of the electronic structures and electronic transitions of the series CH_3F , CH_2F_2 , CHF_3 and CF_4 are presented. Different ground state properties of these molecules as well as empirically adjusted Koopman's theorem calculated ionization potentials are in good agreement with previous ab initio calculations.

THE fluoromethanes provide a series of molecules of increasing electronic complexity with different identifiable trends throughout the series. This makes these substances a target for many experimental and theoretical investigations.

Optical spectra of all the fluoromethanes as well as other halomethanes have been recorded in the vacuum ultraviolet region extending in some cases to beyond 18.6 eV^{-1} ⁸. Also high-resolution photoelectron spectra of all the series of fluoromethanes together with the halomethanes have been studied in details⁹⁻¹¹, and correlated with their vacuum uv absorption spectra, with an unambiguous assignment of almost all of the bands observed¹¹.

On the other hand, theoretical calculations have been performed for the entire series using semi-empirical CNDO method¹²⁻¹⁴ and ab initio method¹⁵⁻²⁰. Mulliken population charge distribution from ab initio wave functions have been analyzed for these molecules in going from CH_3F to CF_4 ^{15,16,18}. Core electron binding energies and shifts in fluoro- and chloromethanes have been predicted from ab initio calculations with various basis sets^{17,20}. Also, ab initio wave functions proved to be an indispensable aid in assigning the photoelectron spectra of these molecules¹¹.

In this paper the results of CNDO/S with configuration interaction calculations of the ground state properties and the different possible electronic transitions are presented for CH_3F , CH_2F_2 , CHF_3 and CF_4 molecules. Also, the Koopman's theorem ionization potential values are compared with previous ab initio results and experimental values, aiming the evaluation of the CNDO/S method for the present type calculations.

Method of calculations :

Calculations were carried out using a CNDO/S program²¹ on the CDC 7600 computer system of

Aberystwyth-UMRCC. The two-centre electron repulsion integrals $\gamma_{\mu\nu}$ are evaluated using the Mataga-Nishimoto relationship²² :

$$\gamma_{\mu\nu} = \frac{e^2}{R + a_{\mu\nu}} \quad \dots (1)$$

$$\text{where } a_{\mu\nu} = \frac{2e^2}{(\gamma_{\mu\mu} + \gamma_{\nu\nu})} \quad \dots (2)$$

The molecules are assumed to be in their experimental molecular geometries²³ with C_{3v} symmetry for CH_3F and CHF_3 molecules and C_{2v} and T_d symmetries for CH_2F_2 and CF_4 molecules, respectively.

Results and Discussion

The CNDO/S calculated ground state molecular properties of fluoromethanes are given in Table 1. The total atomic charges show an interesting behaviour. In CH_3F molecule, the fluorine atom drains charge from the carbon and hydrogen atoms, thus becoming negatively charged with 0.229 more electrons. Upon substitution of fluorine for hydrogen, the positive charges on the remaining hydrogen atoms increase and a parallel pronounced increase of the positive charge on the carbon atom also takes place, but the net amount of negative charge gained by each fluorine atom decreases in going from CH_3F to CF_4 , as expected. In CF_4 molecule the carbon atom loses 0.716 electrons to the fluorines. This behaviour of CNDO/S calculated atomic charges throughout this series of molecules is the same for the ab initio calculated values^{11,18,20}. The CNDO/S calculated atomic charges for CH_3F molecule together with values from ab initio calculations with different basis sets^{10,24,25} are given in Table 2.

Although the CNDO/S atomic charges are rather high, the molecular dipole moments are not very large. This is due to molecular symmetry. The

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TABLE 1—CNDO/S CALCULATED GROUND STATE MOLECULAR PROPERTIES FOR FLUOROMETHANES

	CH ₃ F	CH ₂ F ₂	CHF ₃	CF ₄
At. Charges :	C +0.07847	+0.26862	+0.48063	+0.71579
	H +0.05023	+0.07844	+0.10687	—
	F -0.22916	-0.21275	-0.19584	-0.17895
Dip. Moments ^a	2.243 (1.850)	2.632 (1.960)	2.372 (1.640)	0.0
E _T ^b	-19.0992	-31.4947	-41.3542	-49.0176
Orb. Energies ^b	-42.7506 (3a ₁) -28.1781 (4a ₁) -20.1911 (1e) -19.6965 (5a ₁) -15.1454 (2e)	-46.1950 (3a ₁) -39.5974 (2b ₁) -26.6445 (4a ₁) -22.2016 (1b ₂) -21.6233 (5a ₁) -21.1014 (3b ₁) -18.4367 (1a ₂) -17.6195 (4b ₁) -16.8942 (6a ₁) -14.6246 (2b ₂)	-49.0094 (3a ₁) -40.7472 (2e) -26.0308 (4a ₁) -23.3902 (5a ₁) -22.3786 (3e) -19.1205 (4e) -18.2600 (1a ₂) -17.8565 (5e) -15.4298 (6a ₁)	-51.0573 (3a ₁) -41.7399 (2t ₂) -25.3584 (4a ₁) -23.4835 (3t ₂) -20.0558 (1e) -18.7655 (4t ₂) -18.1460 (1t ₁)

a—in Debyes ; experimental values are given in parentheses.

b—in eV with only valence shell electrons being considered and the beginning symmetry orbitals missing in all cases refer to the inner is orbitals of the C and F atoms in each molecule.

TABLE 2—CNDO/S CALCULATED DIPOLE MOMENT AND ATOMIC CHARGES FOR CH₃F MOLECULE TOGETHER WITH AB INITIO VALUES USING DIFFERENT BASIS SETS

	CNDO/S	ab initio				
		Double Zeta ^a	STO-3G ^b	STO-4G ^c	4-31G ^d	6-31G ^d
At. Charge :	C +0.07847	-0.140	+0.1684	-0.046589	-0.029228	-0.023616
	H +0.05023	+0.174	-0.0044	+0.067539	+0.161992	+0.158655
	F -0.22916	-0.383	-0.1552	-0.156028	-0.456750	-0.452348
Dip. Mom. (D) :	2.243	2.597		1.2236	2.4977	2.4982

a—Ref. 11 ; b—Ref. 19 ; c—Ref. 25 ; d—Ref. 24.

CH₂F₂ molecule with the lowest symmetry (C_{2v}) in the series has the largest calculated dipole moment, 2.63D, which in turn is about 34% larger than the experimental value 1.96D²⁶. For CH₃F and CHF₃ molecules with the C_{3v} symmetry, the calculated dipole moments are 2.24D and 2.37D : about 21% and 45% higher than their experimental values 1.85D and 1.64D, respectively²⁶. The dependence of the ab initio calculated dipole moment of CH₃F molecule on the basis set used is also shown in Table 2.

The CNDO/S calculated orbital energies are in good agreement with the ab initio calculated values^{11, 18}. In CH₃F and CH₂F₂ molecules, the CNDO/S orbital ordering is exactly the same as that obtained by ab initio method. For CF₄ molecule Bassett and Lloyd¹⁴ assigned the orbital ordering 4t₂ < 1t₁ < 1e, but Lempka *et al*¹⁰, based on a correlation of the photoelectron spectra of fluoromethanes with the spectra of other halo-methanes and also Brundle *et al*¹¹ in their study of the photoelectron spectra of fluoromethanes and making use of ab initio results, arrived at the assignment 1t₁ < 4t₂ < 1e orbital ordering. This latter assignment, which places 1t₁ ahead of 4t₂, is maintained here. However, the CNDO/S orbital ordering for CHF₃ molecule is found to be 6a₁ < 5e < 1a₂, while previous ab initio calculation^{11, 18} predicted the ordering 6a₁ < 1a₂ < 5e. Since the orbital energies of the 1a₂ and 5e orbitals are very

close by both CNDO/S and ab initio methods, such ordering would not affect any conclusion very much.

Using the CNDO/S calculated orbital energies, the Koopman's theorem ionization potentials values, empirically reduced for all the fluoromethanes are presented in Table 3. Experiences with Koopman's theorem for obtaining ionization potentials¹¹ or binding energies²⁰ in fluoromethanes have shown an overestimation in Koopman's theorem values compared with experimental values. The fact that Koopman's theorem neglects electronic relaxation suggests that much better agreement with experiment is obtainable if the Koopman's theorem values are empirically reduced to allow for the imperfect cancellation of the reorganization energy and correlation energy errors. Brundle *et al*¹¹ reduced the Koopman's theorem ionization potential values by an empirical scaling factor of 8%, but they found that a 0.8⁵ of the Koopman's theorem value would improve the agreement considerably in case of CF₄ molecule. This latter scaling factor is rather used for all the fluoromethanes. As is clear from Table 3, the CNDO/S calculated ionization potentials agree very well with both ab initio values and the measured adiabatic ionization potentials¹¹.

The results of a limited configuration interaction calculation of the different possible electronic transitions in such series of molecules are presented

TABLE 3—CNDO/S COMPUTED IONIZATION POTENTIALS TOGETHER WITH AB INITIO AND OBSERVED VALUES FOR FLUOROMETHANES (IN eV)

Compound	Orbital	CNDO/S (0.85 K. T.)	ab initio (0.85 K. T.)		Adiabatic ^a
			Double Zeta ^a	Gaussian basis ^b	
CH ₃ F	2e	12.87	12.26	12.06	12.54
	5a ₁	16.74	15.30	14.60	{ 15.80
	1e	17.16	16.06	15.90	
	4a ₁	23.95	22.21	22.36	22.70
CH ₂ F ₂	3a ₁	36.34	36.74	35.93	-
	2b ₂	12.43	12.66	12.55	12.72
	6a ₁	14.36	14.40	13.94	-
	4b ₁	14.98	14.64	14.06	≥14.50
	1a _g	15.67	15.48	14.95	-
	3b ₁	17.94	17.32	16.70	-
	5a ₁	18.38	17.96	17.75	18.20
	1b _g	18.27	18.31	18.29	-
	4a ₁	22.65	22.74	22.94	23.10
	2b ₁	33.66	37.22	36.58	-
CHF ₃	3a ₁	39.27	38.78	38.35	-
	6a ₁	13.12	14.05	14.09	≥13.80
	1a _g	15.52	15.57	15.25	-
	5e	15.18	15.76	15.33	-
	4e	16.25	16.75	16.51	17.11
	3e	19.02	19.44	19.16	{ 26.60
	5a ₁	19.88	20.21	20.22	
	4a ₁	22.13	23.36	23.46	≥24.34
2e	34.64	38.54	38.23	-	
CF ₄	3a ₁	41.66	40.99	40.83	-
	1t ₁	15.42	16.49	-	≥15.35
	4t ₂	15.95	16.71	-	17.10
	1e	17.05	18.14	-	18.30
	3t ₂	19.96	21.16	-	21.70
	4a ₁	21.55	23.93	-	25.12
	2t ₂	35.48	39.65	-	-
	3a ₁	43.40	42.92	-	-

a—Ref. 11 ; b—Ref. 18.

TABLE 4—POSSIBLE ELECTRONIC TRANSITIONS IN FLUOROMETHANES CALCULATED BY CNDO/S METHOD

Compound	Energy (eV)	Excited Singlets		Energy (eV)	Excited Triplets	
		f	Polarization		f	Polarization
CH ₃ F ^a	12.57	0.12	x/y ^a	11.65	0.28	x/y
	14.80	0.20	x/y	13.53	0.18	z
	15.70	0.15	x/y	14.02	0.15	x/y
	17.91	0.13	x/y	16.90	0.09	z
	18.00	0.31	z	-	-	-
CH ₂ F ₂ ^b	12.14	0.20	z	11.07	0.24	z
	15.31	0.32	xy	12.82	0.23	xy
	16.42	0.20	z	15.98	0.06	z
	20.87	0.52	xy	18.44	0.10	xy
	-	-	-	19.54	0.36	xy
CHF ₃ ^b	13.44	0.29	xyz	11.70	0.30	xyz
	16.75	0.08	xyz	18.63	0.18	xyz
	19.17	0.12	xyz	18.91	0.38	xyz
	19.84	0.14	xyz	-	-	-
	20.06	0.29	xyz	-	-	-
CF ₄ ^b	21.13	0.20	xyz	-	-	-
	17.15	0.18	xy	16.44	0.10	xy
	17.26	0.16	xy	16.49	0.11	z
	19.87	0.12	z	16.50	0.17	xy
	20.80	0.06	xy	16.74	0.08	xy
	21.54	0.42	z	19.20	0.29	z
-	-	-	20.74	0.14	z	

c x/y means that the state is either x or y polarized.

in Table 4 where transitions with oscillator strengths less than 0.05 are omitted. In all the molecules the calculated low-lying electronic transitions lie in a high-energy spectral region which is comparable to the calculated ionization potentials. It is worth mentioning that low-lying transitions in fluoromethanes are not expected since the ionization potential of the fluorine atom is over 17 eV, and the observed bands in the optical spectra in the vacuum uv region are either valence shell or Rydberg transitions. All bands observed in the region 8-17 eV have been assigned¹¹ as transitions from the highest occupied molecular orbitals to 3s or 3p Rydberg levels together with the photoelectron spectroscopic ionization potentials.

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